

Expert and Scientific Advice in Public Policymaking in Armenia

Arthur Grigoryan

Abstract

Addressing societal problems by relying on expert advice is commonplace in many developed countries. Two key tools are needed for effective decision-making: access to high-quality, real-time data and the integration of independent expert advice. These tools, it will be argued, are common in advanced democracies but scarce in developing countries such as Armenia. The paper examines and analyzes this shortcoming in four sections. The first section sets out some of the preconditions for high quality expert advice. Section two briefly discusses the legal regulations of expert advice mechanisms in Armenia. The third section highlights aspects of evidence-based policymaking in the United States as a benchmark. Section four illustrates how these principles could apply to Armenia's health system using it as a case study. The paper concludes with some practical recommendations on how to incorporate expert advice into public policymaking in Armenia.

Keywords: expert advice, policymaking, Armenia, advanced democracies, data

Introduction

The 21st century has been marked by unprecedented advancement in technologies. The fastest ever flow of and access to information, emergence of technologies, such as artificial intelligence, has revolutionized traditional industrial patterns worldwide, and profoundly impacted the pace and quality of public policy decision-making. Policy decisions can now be informed by real-time data and advanced analytics.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution popularized by Klaus Schwab (2016), emphasizes the fusion of technologies across different domains and the necessity of new approaches to policies and regulations.

New security threats, such as climate change, overpopulation and underpopulation, and unregulated artificial intelligence, alongside "traditional" threats such as wars, terrorism, pandemics, and natural disasters, have been posing unprecedented challenges for many, if not all, governments. Now more than ever, public policymakers are forced to take fast, efficient, and sustainable choices to address these challenges. Adapting to new technological and scientific breakthroughs is key to effective policymaking.

Addressing societal problems requires two major tools in the arsenal of decision-makers. First, officials entitled by law to make public policy

choices at various levels should have access to valid and evidence-based information in whatever forms possible—summaries, spreadsheets, databases, and analyses. The second essential tool for decision-makers is the prevalence of scientific and expert advice in the decision-making process. The format of the advising body may vary—advisors, advisory bodies, think tanks, research institutions, etc.

These tools, as it will be illustrated further, are common in advanced democracies where there is a greater degree of access to data and established mechanisms for integrating scientific and expert advice into policymaking. Meanwhile, in developing countries such as Armenia, there is a need to establish or expand these capabilities.

In the first section of this paper, I list some of the preconditions for high quality expert advice. Then, I briefly discuss the legal regulations of expert advice mechanisms in Armenia. Third, I articulate some aspects of evidence-based policymaking in the United States as a benchmark. Fourth, I illustrate how these principles could apply to health system in Armenia as an example. Finally, I conclude the paper with a number of feasible recommendations to incorporate expert and scientific advice into public policymaking in Armenia.

Importance of Scientific and Expert Advice in Policymaking

Public policymakers often lack insightful and in-depth knowledge about the diverse issues they encounter when making policy decisions. For this reason, they should extensively rely on the impartial scientific and expert community advice—not merely by choice, but through clear legal and regulatory mechanisms. When done in a transparent and efficient manner, this approach may positively affect the level of public trust in adopted policies. The integrity of scientific data and advice must never be compromised, regardless of political, economic or cultural considerations.

When data and advice are manipulated for political, economic, or other reasons, public trust is eroded. Moreover, in fields such as public health and environmental protection, compromised scientific data and advice can lead to serious public health risks. Reliable scientific data and expert advice are also crucial for setting long-term goals and developing strategies to address them.

Challenges for Strengthening Armenia's Policy Advisory System

In Armenia, the expert and scientific advice in public policy decision-making traditionally hinges on the institute of advisors and ad hoc advisory bodies, as reflected in national legislation.

Not surprisingly, this model is generally not very different from the

practice in place in advanced Western democracies. However, Armenia faces challenges related to the level of independence of advisors, the limited capabilities of the expert community, the lack of well-established research institutions and think tanks, and the deficiency of accurate, well-maintained information databases.

Independence is a crucial factor in ensuring that advisors can offer unbiased and objective advice to policymakers. Any kind of pressure on advisors—such as fear of losing their job or appearing disloyal to a supervisor—may compromise the quality of their recommendations. Independence will allow advisors to prioritize the public interest above all other considerations.

A robust expert community is essential for generating high-quality research and policy analysis. Inadequate funding, insufficient training, and limited opportunities for experts can hinder the development of a skilled and diverse pool of professionals capable of effectively tackling Armenia's unique challenges.

The absence of well-established research institutions and think tanks is another significant barrier. Without them, Armenia lacks a crucial source of credible and comprehensive policy analysis.

Lastly, access to accurate and up-to-date data is fundamental to informed decision-making. The prevalence of inaccurate or incomplete data can lead to flawed policies, further complicating the challenges faced by the country.

Addressing these issues is essential for enhancing the effectiveness of Armenia's policy advisory system and ensuring that decisions are data-driven and impartial.

Legal Aspects of Advisory Institutions in Armenia

The following paragraphs will examine the legal framework for the involvement of advisors in decision-making process. While these regulations seemingly establish a solid base for the normal functioning of the institution of advisors, they also present drawbacks that may undermine the independent and impartial involvement of the scientific community in the process of decision-making, potentially impacting public trust in the entire process. Here a distinction shall be made between advisory bodies within governmental institutions and the independently functioning expert community. This distinction will be further illustrated.

The basic qualifications for an advisory position are listed in Paragraph 5 of Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Armenia on Public Service (Law on Public Service, 2018). According to this law, the positions of advisors to heads of governmental and local government bodies (President of the Republic, Chairman of the National Assembly, Prime-Minister, Deputy Prime

Ministers, Ministers, Governors, and others) are open to "...individuals who are at least 25 years old, possess a higher education degree, and have at least three years of public service or at least three years of work experience in the field required by the job description."

Furthermore, Paragraph 8 of the same article stipulates the job description criteria for advisors. In particular, it establishes a so-called "position passport" for an advisor, specifying that the criteria for the job or the "position passport" are defined by the official under whose supervision or for whom the advisor will work. These criteria are thereafter approved (i.e. formalized) by the chief of staff of the respective institution.

Paragraph 9 of Article 5 states that "the person occupying the position of advisor is appointed to the position without competition, meeting the requirements set by the passport of the given position." Thus, the law sets minimal standards, including basic age and experience requirements, for occupying an advisory position to officials potentially holding highest posts at the state level. These low thresholds, in practice, leave significant room for debate concerning the capability of advisors to provide skilled and informed consultation and advice to high-ranking officials, whose decisions affect key areas of public policy. This is a critical issue in fields such as the environment, public health, foreign policy, and high technologies, which require years of professional and technical training and experience.

Therefore, it may be assumed that the Law on Public Service of Armenia allows the high-ranking officials to hire advisors they deem comfortable working with, rather than those who are more qualified for the job. Thus, there is a pressing need for clearer regulations and mechanisms to ensure the involvement of the scientific community in the policymaking process, safeguarding its independence and impartiality. Furthermore, the minimal standards for appointing advisors may diminish the public's trust in policy choices influenced by such advisors.

The major responsibilities of advisors to high-level officials, such as ministers, reflect those of advisors to the Prime Minister, which are stipulated by law (Rules of Procedure of the Staff of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia, 2018).¹ These responsibilities include drafting action plans and submitting them to the supervisor for approval; studying the areas assigned to them; monitoring development trends in those areas; identifying problems and presenting proposals; regularly submitting analytical and advisory reports; participating in discussions of issues related to their functions as instructed by supervisors; coordinating activities of consultative bodies or taking part in their work upon the decision of supervisors; convening conferences and organizing discussions on assigned issues tasked by supervisors; and performing other tasks delegated by supervisors.

¹ For more details, see: <https://www.arlis.am/DocumentView.aspx?docid=167206>

This framework highlights a predominantly vertical, top-down approach in allocating responsibilities to advisors. In other words, the main functions of advisors are subject to the discretion of their supervisors, whereas ideally, the work of scientific advisors and experts should be explicitly regulated to empower them to gather the best available data independently and present robust policy recommendations. Such a shift is crucial for enhancing the quality and impartiality of advice that influences policymaking.

Evidence-Based Governance: Lessons from the United States

The importance of reliable, high-quality information and decision-making based on such information at different levels is widely recognized in advanced democracies. After briefly discussing expert advice in Armenia in the previous paragraphs, we now turn to the United States, using its experience as a benchmark for several reasons. First, the expert community in the United States provides well-researched policy proposals and recommendations (Drezner, 2017), which can serve as valuable resources for lawmakers and government officials. Second, many think tanks and research institutions in the United States often have access to significant resources, including funding, data, and research tools, allowing them to conduct in-depth studies and analyses (McGann, 2020). This also allows to employ experts with diverse backgrounds and perspectives, which can ultimately lead to more comprehensive and balanced policy recommendations. Third, think tanks and experts can have a substantial influence on policymaking in the United States, as described by both Abelson (2018) and Parmar (2004). Policymakers frequently seek input from experts and rely on their research when crafting legislation and policies. Fourth, the research findings and recommendations of the expert community in the United States often gain global recognition and are influential on an international scale, as again claimed by Abelson (2018). Finally, many research organizations in the United States are both required and voluntarily inclined to be more transparent and accountable in their work, which contributes to the level of trust in their findings and recommendations (Stone, 2007).

Even a country with traditionally solid experience of involving expert community, civil society, academia, and scientists in the decision-making process, such as the United States, continues to explore new mechanisms and approaches in guaranteeing that public institutions and public officials have limited margins of deviation when dealing with scientific data and information, and when engaging with experts to provide it.

In September 2021, the United States Department of State adopted the Enterprise Data Strategy with the aim of ensuring accurate and timely data for the U.S. diplomats. The accumulated expertise reflected in the

database serves as a useful tool for diplomats working in different environments. This is a recent example that demonstrates the importance of data availability in a specific area of public policy. Introducing a similar tool in Armenia could help address the issue of reliable and accessible data for experts and policymakers.

In January 2021, the issue of trust in public policymaking was conceptualized in the United States by the *Memorandum on Restoring Trust in Government Through Scientific Integrity and Evidence-Based Policymaking*, which was adopted for the heads of executive departments and agencies.

The 2021 memorandum highlights the importance of evidence-based policymaking and places responsibility on the heads of respective agencies to ensure that their policies include appropriate evidence. This can be ensured through different methods, including but not limited to pilot projects, quantitative and qualitative research and statistical analysis, and community engagement in research. In this process, it is important that relevant experts and scientists have access to various databases, which they can use in their research and in developing proper recommendations. Ideally, these databases should contain statistical data summarized by different factors, such as gender, age, or income, which would allow experts to properly evaluate the impact of governmental policy on different strata of the population. Scientific integrity across different governmental agencies is ensured by the requirement that each agency have a lead scientific integrity official selected from among senior career employees. Moreover, it should be safeguarded that highly qualified external experts have no difficulties engaging with executive agencies should the latter require their expertise.

Below are several key messages and requirements this memorandum sets with the aim of ensuring scientific integrity across different governmental agencies, which, ultimately, can positively affect the level of public trust in governmental processes and public policymaking:

- Scientific information and data are indispensable to delivering best public policies.
- Politics must not interfere with the work of scientists and experts who advise the government on policy issues; otherwise, this may undermine trust in governmental policies.
- Whenever policy decisions require scientific or technological information, it must be peer reviewed and reliable. It must be ensured across the entire executive branch of government that scientific and technological processes involved in public policymaking are impartial and that data or findings are not distorted or altered in any way to support a particular policy.
- There must be an official responsible for coordinating and ensuring scientific integrity across different areas of government. This role, ac-

ording to the memorandum, is to be carried out by the Director of the Office of Science and Technology Policy.

- Scientific and expert advisors involved in different executive agencies must be independent and impartial. Any conflict of interest must be excluded.

The 2021 memorandum goes further by establishing a Task Force to examine and ensure that existing practices across different governmental agencies are sufficient to prevent political interference in scientific research, including the distortion of scientific findings and data. One of the crucial assignments of the Task Force is to ensure whether “effective reporting practices” are in place in order to prevent misconduct and political interference and to guarantee the transparency of scientific research, its delivery, and the submission of findings and conclusions.

The conduct of governmental officials, when it comes to ensuring scientific integrity within their respective agencies, must be based on the following principles outlined in the 2009 Presidential Memorandum:

- A candidate’s knowledge, credentials, experience, and integrity must be instrumental in their selection for science, expert, or technology positions in the executive branch.
- Expert and scientific integrity within an agency must be based on well-established rules and regulations.
- When expert, scientific, and technological information is considered in public policy decisions, it must be peer reviewed, and there must be an appropriate mechanism to incorporate that information into the relevant decision.
- Expert, scientific, and technological data or findings (except those classified by law) involved in public policy decisions must be open and easily accessible to the public.
- Proper mechanisms must be in place to address situations in which scientific or expert data is compromised in whatever forms.
- Additional measures must be taken to ensure scientific integrity, including the whistleblower protection.

The necessity of the public policies to be hinged on properly collected impartial scientific data, as well as the mechanisms for addressing this, is reflected in the *Foundations for Evidence-Based Policymaking Act of 2018* (U.S. Public Law 115-435). According to paragraph 312 of the act, a strategic and evaluation plan of the governmental agency must include:

1. “A list of policy-relevant questions for which the agency intends to develop evidence to support policymaking.”

This can be considered the initial step in ensuring scientific integrity within an agency, as it formulates why, at later stages of policymaking, scientific data must be collected, and the scientific and expert

community must be involved. For example, at the very early stages of approximating tobacco control policies in Armenia to World Health Organization (WHO) standards, a fact sheet was developed that aimed to answer the following questions: Can the premature death of tobacco smokers be explained by tobacco use? And what might be the effects of tobacco control policies on smoking prevalence and smoking-attributable deaths?

2. "A list of data the agency intends to collect, use, or acquire to facilitate the use of evidence in policymaking."

Here, the key focus is on what information should be collected or what the agency needs to examine in order to support or discontinue its policy. Using the example of tobacco control policy again, the data collected to demonstrate the effectiveness of the policy—or to highlight its benefits—included the prevalence of smoking among men and women, as well as the projected number of premature deaths among smokers.

3. "A list of methods and analytical approaches that may be used to develop evidence to support policymaking."

This requirement addresses how the data should be collected. In case of the tobacco control policy, the data was based on a nationwide representative survey, as well as the 2015 WHO report on the global tobacco epidemic.

4. "A list of any challenges to developing evidence to support policymaking, including any statutory or other restrictions to accessing relevant data."

Here, the emphasis is placed on the necessity of conducting legal research to reveal any possible gaps and/or regulatory restrictions that may impede the evidence development process.

5. "A description of steps the agency will take to accomplish requirements set in paragraphs 1 and 2."

This point highlights the issue of transparency and accountability—both essential for the development of long-term goals and strategies.

In paragraph 312, section (c) of the act, the head of the agency, while developing the strategic and evaluation plan for the agency, "shall consult with stakeholders, including the public, agencies, state and local governments, and representatives of non-governmental researchers." The requirement to involve non-governmental researchers is crucial for engaging civil society actors in the policy planning process. The meticulous details the act provides in describing the requirements for data and evidence collection in governmental policy development leaves little room for officials to distort, misinterpret, or otherwise abuse scientific data and findings. An example of such details is the establishment of the Act of the Advisory Committee on Data for Evidence Building (paragraph 315, sec-

tion (a)), which involves officers such as the “Chief Information Officer,” “Chief Privacy Officer,” “Chief Performance Officer,” “Chief Data Officers,” and others.

Post-COVID Healthcare System Adjustment in Armenia: Insights and Possible Strategies

Given the above points are applied, for example, to the case of post-COVID healthcare system adjustment in Armenia, the following would have been the questions and tasks for the Ministry of Health.²

Policy-relevant questions: How can Armenia strengthen its healthcare system to better handle future pandemics or health crises? What are the lessons learned from the COVID-19 response, and how can these inform future healthcare policies? How can digital health solutions be integrated into the healthcare system to enhance accessibility and efficiency?

List of data to collect or use: Epidemiological data related to COVID-19 cases and the healthcare system’s response; data on healthcare infrastructure, including hospital capacity, equipment, and healthcare workforce; and surveys to gather feedback from healthcare professionals and the public on their pandemic experiences and needs.

List of methods and analytical approaches: Analyzing COVID-19 data and response measures to identify strengths and weaknesses; engaging healthcare experts; and conducting pandemic and post-pandemic scenario exercises.

Challenges to developing evidence: Potential challenges for the Ministry might have included limited experience in dealing with a pandemic of this scale in Armenia, as well as budgetary and regulatory constraints for implementing digital health solutions.

Steps to accomplish requirements: Seek international partnerships and funding to support data collection and analysis; establish a dedicated task force comprising healthcare experts, researchers, and policymakers; and develop a comprehensive post-COVID healthcare adjustment plan based on the evidence gathered.

Role of think tank community in the United States as a benchmark: To ensure meaningful expert and scientific involvement in public policymaking in Armenia, the most effective approach could be the establishment of institutions similar to think tanks commonly found in advanced democracies, particularly in the United States. The U.S. model serves as a benchmark and an ideal point of reference, offering a potential pathway for the development of Armenia’s research organizations and expert community.

² The example of post-COVID healthcare system adjustment in Armenia is brought for illustrative purposes only and does not necessarily reflect the actual activities of the Ministry of Health of Armenia in the post-COVID period.

When discussing expert and scientific advice in public policymaking, the role of think tanks cannot be underestimated, especially in the United States.

According to Alexander Ruser (2018), providing a clear definition of think tanks is a difficult task due to the lack of uniformity in their structures, strategic goals, and operating mechanisms.

One definition of think tanks can be found in the research of Andrew Rich, who describes them as “independent, noninterest-based, nonprofit political organizations that produce and principally rely on expertise and ideas to obtain support and to influence the policymaking process” (Rich, 1999, p.19).

According to *The Economist*, “Think-tanks aim to fill the gap between academia and policymaking” (*The Economist*, 2017).

Think tanks in the United States vary in their missions, strategic goals, adherence to parties or nonpartisanship, and the focus on foreign policy, domestic policy, or both.

Some of the major think tanks in the United States—most of which are independent, non-profit organizations—identify themselves as non-partisan, focusing on foreign policies and international agenda, such as the Atlantic Council. Others, such as the Heritage Foundation, focus more on the protection of conservative values in American society and are widely supported by the U.S. Republican Party. There are also think tanks such as the Center for American Progress that concentrate more on domestic and economic policy agendas, prioritizing the economic prosperity and the wellbeing of the American people in their strategic activities. Hundreds of research organizations in the United States work to identify the major challenges facing both the country and the world. They engage top professionals, scientists, and experts across various fields to generate ideas for addressing those challenges. Their findings and discussions are often compiled into publications and reports, which serve as indispensable tools for policymakers to make informative and solid choices—ideally most beneficial to the public.

The tools think tanks utilize when trying to influence public policymaking are various. They include the publication of books and articles, the organization of seminars and conferences, the coordination of a vast network of professionals across various fields, and the provision of trainings and leadership courses for potential future leaders, among others.

There is still an ongoing debate about the actual level of influence that think tanks have on final policy choices, partly because they differ from advisory bodies. A distinction should be made between think tanks and advisory bodies in the United States, primarily in terms of independence, organizational structure, functions, and affiliations. Think tanks are independent research organizations that generate policy recommendations

through research and analysis, while advisory bodies are government-affiliated entities formed to provide specialized advice to government agencies or officials within a specific policy area. Both play important roles in informing and influencing policymaking, but they operate in distinct ways.

On Measurement of Influence of Think Tanks

The level of influence exerted by think tanks is very hard to evaluate, as noted by Abelson (2002), who undertakes the difficult task of measuring their actual impact within the political environments of different systems in the United States and Canada. However, it can be objectively argued that the current quality and level of development of think tanks allows us to conclude that, at a minimum, they shape discussions across various spheres, are capable of engaging top experts and professionals in relevant fields, and, ultimately, narrow the number of policy choices. Abelson, rather than attempting to measure the influence of the think tanks merely by the number of media citations, appearances of the think tank staff in the testimonies of legislative committees, or the volume of their publications, focuses instead on the opportunities of influence on public policy, as well as the internal and external constraints they face (2000, p. 215). He suggests that a think tank's ability to "sell" its ideas is determined not so much by the political system in which it operates, but rather by "how these institutions define their mission, the directors who lead them, and the resources and strategies they employ to achieve their stated goals..." (p. 215).

Abelson illustrates different waves of the development of think tanks by describing changes in their roles, capacities, and working methods over time (2000, pp. 217-223). He describes the first wave as the establishment of policy research institutions that concentrated most of their intellectual and financial resources on studying different policy issues (e.g., Brookings, Carnegie, Hoover).

The second wave of think tanks is labeled by Abelson as the "government contractors." He argues that this wave emerged primarily in the aftermath of the World War II, when policymakers were facing unprecedented challenges related to both domestic and international post-war agendas. As a result, they began contracting research institutions to examine these issues and support policy options. It is in this wave of the development of think tanks that the U.S. government hinged upon the expertise of engineers, biologists, social scientists, and others, in order to confront the post war realities. One of the most prominent think tanks established during this period was RAND (1948), abbreviated from "research and development," whose main contractor was the Department of Defense.

The third wave is described as the age of "advocacy think tanks." According to the author, this period marks the transformation of think tanks

from purely research-based institutions into “advocacy and interest group” entities (the Heritage Foundation), promoting and lobbying their ideas and approaches among policymakers and ultimately claiming a “seat” in the political policymaking process. Abelson claims that during this process of transformation from “research institutions” to “political advocacy”- type organizations, think tanks lost some of their legitimacy among both scholars and policymakers.

Abelson identifies the fourth wave of think tank development as the wave of “vanity and legacy-based” institutions, established primarily by the former presidents and other former high office holders. He describes these think tanks as tools the former high-ranking officials to promote their agendas well beyond their terms in office. As early as in 2000, Abelson cited examples such as the Carter Center and the Nixon Center for Peace and Freedom. More contemporary examples of institutions that fit this category include the McCain Institute for International Leadership at Arizona State University and the Obama Foundation.

Regarding the reasons for think tanks’ success in their relationships with policymakers, Abelson emphasizes their vast networks of top academics and former policymakers, which serve as an incentive for current policymakers to benefit from their expertise.

Another reason for the close interconnectivity between the political establishment and think tanks is that many experts affiliated with different think tanks often go on to occupy various governmental positions, thereby reinforcing the ideologies of those think tanks in policymaking.

Around the same time that Abelson was engaged in studying the influence of think tanks in the United States and Canada, Andrew Rich suggested that think tanks have become more “market-oriented” and more ideological, blurring the line between experts and advocates. Rich claims that the traditional role of experts— independent and alienated from politics—has shifted toward that of short-term policy influencers.

Even if independent and impartial experts exist, along with think tanks possessing idea-generating and research capacities, this alone is not sufficient for efficient policymaking. As Elizabeth Saunders argues (2017), regardless of the expertise level of advisors in a group decision-making process, it cannot substitute for the expertise of the leader or decision-maker. Using the two Iraq wars (1991 and 2003) as case studies, she concludes that three mechanisms— monitoring, delegation, and diversification— should be considered when decisions are made based on expert advice, depending on the leader’s level of experience.

In terms of *monitoring*, Saunders explains that the experience of decision-makers affects their ability to monitor the work of advisors. It can be reasonably assumed that an inexperienced leader lacks the tools and likely the ability to effectively monitor and control how the information is

aggregated by their advisors.

Delegation is significant in making correct choices in which tasks are assigned to which advisors and/or experts. Accurate tasking to experienced advisors would be the key factor in guaranteeing effective results.

As to the ability to *diversify* from the submitted choices, this should consider the most prominent stage in the decision-making process. Regardless of the high standards maintained by advisors in data collection, analysis, summarization, and presentation, the final outcome of a given policy depends on the experience level of the person who is legally or otherwise authorized to choose among the available options and make the final decision.

Concluding Observations and Recommendations

Stemming from the discussion above on the current state of legal and practical mechanisms for expert and scientific engagement in policymaking in Armenia, and the existing institutional mechanisms in this area in the United States, some short, mid-, and long-term strategic steps may be identified that could potentially ensure proper scientific integrity in policymaking processes.

In terms of the short-term improvements to existing practices in Armenia, tightening the minimum legal requirements for holding the position of advisor to policymakers, along with the introduction of more rigid and relevant mechanisms of their selection and appointment, could be an initial step. For example, raising the minimum thresholds for age and experience levels of advisors to high-level officials may be relevant. The goal of this endeavor should be to ensure the consideration and appointment of the most qualified candidates and top professionals in the field. This will potentially enhance the “acceptance” of such experts by both the scientific community and the public, thereby increasing trust in policymaking processes within the country.

Another useful mechanism would be the development of a transparent system and practice for expert and scientific involvement in the decision-making process. Here it should be emphasized that calling for public discussions on a given issue is not sufficient. There should be safeguards in place to ensure that independent experts and scientists are necessarily involved in the process, regardless of the discretion of policymakers.

The establishment of a designed position in every policymaking institution (either as a newly-appointed official or by assigning this role to a senior official within the organization) responsible for ensuring proper scientific engagement and coordinating the process of expert and scientific engagement can serve as another feasible option. Nevertheless, this official must act in line with their responsibilities clearly outlined in legislation

and be granted minimal personal discretion. Ensuring the impartiality of this official should be a top priority. To achieve this goal, legal and regulatory clauses should ensure the following:

- Clear guidelines and codes of conduct for these officials
- Transparent processes for their selection
- Requirement to disclose any potential conflicts of interest, whether political, financial, or otherwise
- Term limits to prevent the entrenchment of particular individuals or interests
- Input and feedback from diverse stakeholders to ensure that expert advice is balanced and reflective of broader societal interests
- Mechanisms for peer review and evaluation of expert advice
- Accountability measures and consequences for expert advisors who violate impartiality guidelines or engage in unethical behavior

From a mid-term perspective, drafting a document on expert and scientific engagement in policymaking—analogue to the U.S. memorandums mentioned earlier— would be beneficial, at the very least, in drawing attention to the issue and emphasizing the importance of scientific and expert advice in decision-making.

Advisors and independent experts, regardless of their level of experience and knowledge, cannot function effectively without access to comprehensive databases across various areas. Therefore, steps should be taken to develop appropriate databases in different sectors and/or to make existing ones more user-friendly and accessible.

From a long-term perspective, the development of “think tank” type research institutions in Armenia may be the most effective solution for ensuring proper expert involvement in policymaking and facilitating the adoption of the best policy choices across various areas. The discussion of think tank development in the United States demonstrated that this is a long-term process, with such institutions advancing in parallel with democratic development processes in Armenia. This will also require enormous human, expert, and financial resources. A promising starting point could be the establishment of specialized policy-oriented (environmental, healthcare, economic, vulnerable groups, etc.) research organizations that concentrate their research and analysis on the most pressing issues facing Armenian society. These institutions would also hold the potential to contribute to informed policymaking in Armenia.

From a long-term perspective, investments should be directed toward the education and training of the expert community. The Armenian government, philanthropic organizations, and international donors can provide funding and resources to support the establishment and growth of research institutions and think tanks in Armenia. Investments in data

collection and management systems can help ensure the availability of accurate and well-maintained information, while collaborations with international organizations can enhance data quality. Transparency measures, including disclosure of funding sources for research and advisory activities, can help build public trust in the advisory process and ensure accountability. Finally, Armenia's diaspora should be actively involved, with its skilled professionals and experts who can contribute to the country's development.

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